

UNVEILING THE AVIATION AND AEROSPACE STUDENTS' ANXIETY OF PUBLIC SPEAKING AND CLASSROOM PRESENTATION IN ENGLISH: BASIS FOR POLICY MAKING AND SCHOOL-BASED TRAINING

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ABSTRACT

Public speaking and classroom presentation anxiety among students have been long-standing issues in educational settings. This research aims to determine the relationship of students' presentation anxiety to their academic performance as well as to have an in-depth exploration of their experiences, feelings, tribulations and the overall impact of presentation anxiety in their lives. On the basis of descriptive and sequential study design, this academic paper utilizes an eclectic approach in extracting data through a procedural phase critically following the mixed methods explanatory sequential research methods. An initial investigation on the level of oral presentation anxiety of the aviation and aerospace students was conducted in quantitative part, the Personal Report of Public Speaking Anxiety (PRPSA) instrument by McCroskey (1986) was adapted. It was administered by the researcher together with the demographic profile. Qualitative part followed, where the researcher conducted an open-ended interview with those students who were identified to have a high level of anxiety. It was revealed that public speaking and oral presentation anxiety among students does not have a significant effect on their Grade Point Average ($Z=0.49$, $p=0.621$). In terms of the students' profile, the tribe of students significantly affects their PRPSA level ($Z=-1.99$, $P=0.046$). However, regardless of age, gender, household members and economic status of students, their PRPSA level remains unaffected ($Z=1.01$, -0.40 , -0.36 , -0.20 , $P=0.313$, 0.687 , 0.715 , 0.845). The most common themes revealed that the students feel nervous, afraid of judgments, lack of confidence, pressure, self-consciousness and overwhelming stage fright during oral presentations.

Keywords: *Aviation, Aerospace, PRPSA, public speaking anxiety, grade-point average*

INTRODUCTION

“Most people would want to be the person in the coffin rather than the person delivering the eulogy,” (Rush, 2023).

Seventy-eight percent of students suffer from public speaking and twenty-six percent confirmed extreme case for such (Plandanao *et al.*, 2023). The thought of making mistakes or being perceived as incompetent can be overwhelming and can lead to feelings of self-doubt and insecurity. There are multifarious reasons why people eventually develop a fear of public speaking. One of the major factors is the fear of being criticized by others. Additionally, the apprehension of forgetting what to say or stumbling over words can contribute to the anxiety associated with public speaking. Another contributing factor to the fear of public speaking is the dread of rejection or humiliation. The idea of being laughed at or ridiculed by others can be a powerful deterrent for individuals who already struggle with self-confidence. This is even eminent in the classroom as a large number of students may evade presentation activities such as reporting that requires speaking, which greatly affects their academic performance leading to poor evaluation.

As good evaluation is imperative and compulsive in the academic setting, a number of students from around the world have experienced in their student life at least one of the different types of study anxiety. Study anxiety can be referred to as an underlying source of students' fears during their study process, which include exam anxiety, social anxiety, mathematics anxiety, language anxiety, family anxiety, library anxiety and presentation anxiety (Vitasari *et al.*, 2010). Among these forms of study anxiety, what is most commonly observed in a typical classroom is the oral presentation anxiety, especially in subjects using English as a classroom language. Presentation anxiety is the fear experienced by students when giving presentations. A study conducted by Raja (2017) provides sufficient results that prove that this fear is evident among university students. This is not so surprising given the fact that within the newest trends in educational setting, presentation is a part of classroom proceedings, in which teaching Andragogy (Adult Education Psychology or Adult Learning Theory) is emphasized rather than Pedagogy. Andragogy is a powerful concept that revolutionizes the way educators approach adult education emphasizing the distinctive characteristics and needs of adult learners; therefore, focusing on the adult-learning approach at the center of the educational process and dictates that students are stakeholders in producing abstractions, new knowledge and preponderant ideas (Knowles, 1980).

The claims of the above-mentioned studies correspond with the researcher's own observation and experiences as a university instructor of English Language disciplines. This academic portfolio seeks to determine the presentation anxiety in actuality common

among college students, particularly amongst English classroom settings in an aviation university from Lapu-Lapu City.

Research Questions

This study investigated the impact of presentation anxiety on aviation and aerospace students. Through this inquiry, the study seeks to address the existing gap in literature regarding presentation anxiety among students in high-cost, English-intensive fields, despite their presumed proficiency.

Specifically, this study answered the following questions:

1. What is the relationship between presentation anxiety and the academic performance of aviation and aerospace students?
2. How are the experiences, emotions, and challenges impact the overall performance of aviation and aerospace students?
3. What sound recommendations can be proposed based on the findings?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This research study on unveiling the anxiety related to public speaking and classroom presentations in English utilized a mixed-method research approach, particularly the sequential explanatory design. Mixed methods research was an approach to inquiry involving the collection of both quantitative and qualitative data, integrating the two forms of data, and using distinct designs that involved philosophical assumptions and theoretical frameworks (Creswell, 2014). The core assumption of this form of inquiry was that the combination of quantitative and qualitative approaches provided a more detailed understanding of a research problem than using an independent approach alone.

The sequential explanatory (or explanatory sequential), one of the three basic designs in the mixed methods approach, was a design in which the researcher first conducted quantitative research, analyzed the results, and then backed up the results to explain them in more comprehensive detail with qualitative investigations. It was considered sequential because the initial quantitative phase was followed by the qualitative phase (Creswell, 2014). Findings from both quantitative and qualitative phases were integrated during the data-interpretation stage. The general aim of this approach was to further explain the phenomenon under study qualitatively or to explore the findings of the quantitative study in more depth and with higher critical analysis (Tashakkori and Teddlie, 2010). The design was contemplatively chosen because qualitative data were also gathered to provide pseudo-critical level of context extractions to the quantitative results.

Phase one geared towards acquiring data on the level of presentation anxiety of the aviation and aerospace students, different profiles of the students, and the significant relationship between their presentation anxiety level and their academic performance. Phase two explored the participants' psychological perspectives during a class presentation, the factors that triggered the presentation anxiety, their experiences regarding the dilemma, their ways of dealing with presentation anxiety, and the effects on their academic performance and their lives as a whole. Finally, phase three capitulated the results from the quantitative responses using statistical formulas and then supplemented them by the qualitative explications to provide in-depth and holistic analysis of the research inquiry on the basis of explanatory sequential mixed methods.

As an educator who had witnessed the predicaments of students with presentation anxiety in classes where English was used as a classroom language, it was not only important to conduct a quantitative description of data to determine the relationship of presentation anxiety to the academic performance of the students. Furthermore, it was far more important to have a deeper sense of understanding of the students' experiences, feelings, tribulations, and the overall impact of presentation anxiety in their lives.

Research Locale

This study was conducted in the researcher's workplace which is an aviation university, the first and presently the only aerospace university in the Philippines, located on the island of Mactan. This institution of learning offered Basic and Tertiary levels of quality education. It inculcated academic excellence and universal values. It was located in the subsets of Mactan Island, particularly on Kagudoy Road, Basak Lapu-Lapu City. It produced globally competitive graduates with a lifelong commitment to Aerospace knowledge and skills development and academic pursuits through advanced instruction, production, research, and community service. It was to be noted that, as a major institution where many foreign (non-Filipino citizens) learners were admitted, English was the primary language of instructions.

Participants

The participants of the study were aviation and aerospace students ranging from first to fourth years of tertiary education, who were officially enrolled in aviation university of Lapu-Lapu City in the academic year 2023–2024. Specifically, these students were taking the courses: Bachelor of Science in Aviation and Bachelor of Science in Aerospace Engineering.

Population and Sampling Technique

The target population for this study was the Bachelor of Science in Aviation Technology and the Bachelor of Science in Aerospace Engineering students who were enrolled during the first semester 2023–2024. It was notably emphasized that the grades acquired by the aforementioned students (the research respondents/participants) obtained in the previous semester served as the basis for academic performance. The

lists of all BSAT and BSAE students were obtained from the Registrar's Office, and then using the Slovin's formula $n = N / (1 + Ne^2)$, the sample size was determined.

From the total population of 1,060 students enrolled in the Bachelor of Science in Aviation Technology and the Bachelor of Science in Aerospace Engineering, the researcher took representative samples per block from first year to fourth year of their studies. Through the use of the Slovin's formula, the result yielded a total of 290 respondents to take part in the research process. It was noted that the representative sampling underwent a stringent process using the systematic random number in aid of the random number generator to mechanize objectivity in finding the research samples.

For the Phase 1—Quantitative part of this sequential mixed methods study, the systematic random sampling technique was employed. From the list, the samples were drawn using the random number generator until the required number of samples was completed. From the fourteen sections from all year levels presently employed as the target population, each section was subsequently subjected to the process of determining the individual respondent's sample size through the use of the Slovin's formula.

In Phase 2 – Upon determining the sample population from each section, the qualitative part of this mixed-method study, then commenced. The purposive sampling technique was utilized. Owing to the nature of the sequential design of this study, the participants were selected based on the results of the quantitative phase. It was therefore imperative that in using the explanatory design, the quantitative results of determining the sample population through the Slovin's formula were also the same sample population to be purposefully selected as best participants for qualitative study (Creswell, 2012).

Using the data obtained from the quantitative phase, the level of presentation anxiety of the students was determined; hence the results from phase 1 were used in identifying the respondents for Phase 2, which was the qualitative phase of data gathering. Those students who were found to have a "high level of presentation anxiety" (if the PRPSA score was above 131) were purposefully chosen as participants for Phase 2 - Qualitative part. Obtaining the results from the quantitative part, the researcher then proceeded to purposive sampling in choosing the participants based on appropriate characteristics of sample members or preselected criteria to serve a purpose relevant to a particular research question (Creswell, 2008). To qualify as participants in the second phase, the participants should have had a high level of presentation anxiety so that they could share their feelings and experiences pertaining to presentation anxiety.

Research Instruments

For phase one (the quantitative phase), the research instrument was composed of two parts. Part 1 of the questionnaire covered the socio-demographic profile and the academic performance (GPA incurred during the previous semester). Part 2 of the research instrument determined the level of presentation anxiety of the aviation and aerospace students.

To measure the oral presentation anxiety level of the participants, an adapted instrument was used. This instrument was known as the Personal Report of Public Speaking Anxiety (PRPSA), a validated scale tailored for public speaking anxiety. The PRPSA was an excellent measure for research centered on public speaking anxiety, which was why the researcher modified it to fit this research study's focus on oral presentation anxiety. The PRPSA was also used by several authors in their studies, such as: "General Communication Anxiety among EFL Students; a Case of Iranian Students of Intensive English Programs" by Hassani and Rajab (2012); "Anxiety in Oral Presentations among ITB Students" by Munohsamy et al. (2015); "Stress to Success: Public Speaking Anxiety and its Relationship to Perceived Leadership" (Arnold, 2018); and "A Study on the EFL Students' Speech Related Anxiety in Taiwan" (Hsu Tsu, 2012).

The Personal Report of Public Speaking Anxiety was a research instrument developed by McCroskey (2013) with the primary purpose of measuring public speaking as a form of self-reported communication apprehension. Self-report devices were a preferred approach to obtaining data when the subject knew the answer and was willing to tell the truth, as opposed to wanting to convey a socially desirable image. Given that participants were assured that all information they provided was strictly confidential, with no possibility of anyone other than the third-party data entry person being able to connect any data with participant identities, it was assumed that resulting data comprised honest self-assessments by participants (McCroskey, 1986 cited in Arnold, 2018).

The PRPSA was a unidimensional, 34-item self-report measure of public speaking anxiety that generated high reliability estimates, with Cronbach's alpha (α) $>.90$ and 10-day test-retest reliability of $.84$ (Bodie, 2010 cited in Arnold, 2018). The time needed to answer the instrument was approximately 10-15 minutes. The respondents were asked to rate from five (5) scales (Strongly Disagree = 1, Disagree = 2, Neutral = 3, Agree = 4, or Strongly Agree = 5) on various statements regarding speech anxiety.

Scoring was accomplished by following these steps: Step 1. Add scores for items 1, 2, 3, 5, 9, 10, 13, 14, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 25, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31, 32, 33, and 34; Step 2. Add the 13 scores for items 4, 6, 7, 8, 11, 12, 15, 16, 17, 18, 24, and 26; and Step 3. Complete the following formula: $PRPSA = 72 - \text{Total from Step 2} + \text{Total from Step 1}$. Furthermore, the total score should have fallen between 34 and 170, and if the score was below 34 or above 170, there could have been a mistake in the computation. Oral presentation anxiety was considered high if the score was above 131, low if below 98, and moderate if the score was between 98 and 131.

For phase two (the Qualitative phase of this mixed methods study), the research tool that was used was a researcher-made interview schedule, a list containing a set of structured questions that had been prepared to serve as a guide for the interviewers/researchers in collecting information or data.

Data Gathering Procedure

An initial investigation on the level of oral presentation anxiety of the aviation and aerospace students was conducted in Phase 1-Quantitative part, using the adapted Personal Report of Public Speaking Anxiety (PRPSA) instrument by McCroskey (1986). It was administered by the researcher together with the demographic profile. Aside from asking them to answer the Personal Report of Public Speaking Anxiety (PRPSA) instrument, the participants were asked to provide some demographic information such as age, gender, tribe, and other details. They were also asked to indicate their GPA incurred in the previous semester.

After securing another informed consent, Phase 2-Qualitative part followed, where the researcher conducted an open-ended interview with those students who were identified to have a high level of anxiety. The participants were asked to share their feelings, tribulations, experiences, and the overall impact of presentation anxiety in their lives. Participants were informed that the interview would be recorded, and their permission was sought to record the conversation.

Data Analysis

For the Phase 1-Quantitative part, the demographic profile of the respondents was subjected to descriptive statistics. Then, the students' scores in the PRPSA were computed following the scoring steps discussed in the instrumentation part of this study. Once all the PRPSA scores were available, they were subjected to statistical analysis using Minitab. To determine the effect of presentation anxiety on the academic performance of the aviation and aerospace students, the binary logistic regression analysis was done. To find out if there were significant effects of the demographic profile of aviation and aerospace students in terms of age, gender, tribe, household members, and economic status on PRPSA scores, the ordinal logistic regression analysis was used.

For phase two, the qualitative part, the data gathered from the interviews were transcribed and analyzed qualitatively, following the six stages of thematic analysis by Braun and Clarke (2013): (1) familiarization through reading and rereading the interview transcript; (2) generating the initial codes; (3) creating the initial themes; (4) reviewing the themes; (5) *naming* and defining the themes; and (6) writing the final report. The data were coded and analyzed, guided by the study's objective to explore the students' experiences and feelings about their presentation anxiety.

RESULTS

Table 1
Binary Logistic Regression Analysis Result for the Possible Effect of PRPSA on GPA

Predictor	Coef	SE Coef	Z	P	Odds Ratio	95% CI Lower	95% CI Upper
Constant	-0.114114	0.772933	-0.15	0.883			
PRPSA Score	0.0033720	0.0068229	0.49	0.621	1.00	0.99	1.02

Log-Likelihood = -198.394

Test that all slopes are zero: G = 0.245, DF = 1, P-Value = 0.621

Table 2
Ordinal Logistic Regression Analysis Results for the Effect of Age, Gender, Tribe, Household Members, and Economic Status on PRPSA

Predictor	Coef	SE Coef	Z	P	Odds Ratio	95% CI Lower	95% CI Upper
Const(1)	-0.987979	0.672222	-1.47	0.142			
Const(2)	2.47550	0.693087	3.57	0.000			
Age	0.255792	0.253562	1.01	0.313	1.29	0.79	2.12
Gender	-0.109708	0.271819	-0.40	0.687	0.90	0.53	1.53
Tribe	-0.550310	0.276349	-1.99	0.046*	0.58	0.34	0.99
Household Members	-0.0515413	0.141312	-0.36	0.715	0.95	0.72	1.25
Economic Status	-0.0326167	0.166973	-0.20	0.845	0.97	0.70	1.34

* Significant at 0.05 level of significance

Log-Likelihood = -238.605

Test that all slopes are zero: G = 6.083, DF = 5, P-Value = 0.298

Table 3
Common Categories Transcribed on the Feelings During Class Presentations

Themes Derived		
anxiety	shame	Timidity
nervousness	failure	Intimidation
fear	humiliation	Anguish
panic	frustration	Unease
worry	dread	Resentment
embarrassment	discomfort	Overwhelm
self-consciousness	apprehension	Mortification
insecurity	paranoia	Regret

Table 4
Common Categories Transcribed on the Reasons or Causes of Participants' Presentation Anxiety

Themes Derived		
Fear of judgment	Peer pressure	Feeling of being watched
Lack of confidence	Fear of embarrassment	Lack of speaking skills
Negative past experiences	Lack of control	Stage fright
Fear of failure	Unfamiliarity with audience	Attention-seeking
perfectionism	Feeling of being judged	Vulnerability
Lack of preparation	High expectations	Negativity
Feeling of inadequacy	Performance anxiety	Lack of moral support
Self-consciousness	Fear of making mistakes	Imposter problem

Table 5
Common Categories Transcribed on the Factors that Contribute Most to the Presentation Anxiety

Themes Derived		
Fear of public speaking	Lack of confidence	Lack of self-control
Lack of experience	Lack of preparation	Social anxiety
Low self-esteem	Incompetence	Fear of not engaging

Negative self-talk	Lack of practice	Lack of familiarity
Judgment from others	Unrealistic expectations	Fear of losing authority
Performance pressure	Comparison with others	Fear of failure
Fear of forgetting	Fear of mistakes	Lack of support
Fear for focused attention	Traumatic past experience	Lack of encouragement

Table 6
Common Categories Transcribed on the Ways to Deal with Their Presentation Anxiety

Themes Derived		
Preparation	Mindfulness techniques	Focusing on audience
Deep breathing	Taking breaks to de-stress	Seeking feedback
Visualization	Regular exercise	Setting expectations
Positive self-talk	Developing communication	Positive visualization
Cognitive reframing	Seeking guidance	Relaxation techniques
Gradual exposure	Using humor	Accepting nervousness
Seeking support	Embracing imperfection	Positive self-affirmation
Practicing relaxation	Rehearsing	Celebrating victories

DISCUSSION

According to Harris (2021), Binary logistic regression is a statistical method used to model the relationship between a binary dependent variable (also known as the outcome or response variable) and one or more independent variables (also known as predictors or explanatory variables). The dependent variable takes on only two values, typically representing the presence or absence of an event or outcome.

Table 1 presents a result showing that regardless of PRPSA level of students, their GPA remains unaffected ($Z=0.49$, $p=0.621$).

On the basis of the study environment, public speaking anxiety is a common issue that many individuals face, and it is no surprise that students may experience this anxiety when delivering speeches or presentations in an academic setting. While one might assume that the level of anxiety a student experiences during public speaking could

potentially impact their overall grade in the course, this research findings suggest otherwise.

Overall, the phenomenon of compensatory evaluation helps to explain why student grades are not significantly affected by their public speaking and oral presentation anxiety. Instructors recognize the challenges that students with anxiety face and take steps to evaluate them in a comprehensive and fair manner, considering multiple aspects of their performance and strengths in different areas. Thus, the students' Grade Point Average One possible explanation for this lack of correlation between public speaking anxiety and students' grades is that instructors often use multiple criteria when assigning grades for oral presentations. Collins & Lindström (2021) offer guidance on assessing student performance across various learning assessments, particularly for students with learning difficulties. These criteria may include content knowledge, organizational skills, delivery style, and visual aids, among others. Therefore, even if a student experiences high levels of anxiety, they can still excel in other aspects of the presentation, leading to a favorable grade. A qualitative assessment with the instructor's intervention on grading student's performance is a factor that may lift performance evaluation instead of fully focusing on public speaking and oral presentations where students are mostly tolled in acing good grades. Haskell (2013) noted that a focus on grading can in fact prevent learners from engaging in the process of assessment and learning from their mistakes. Instead, formative assessment should be learning-oriented and provide qualitative feedback rather than assigning a grade. Done this way, formative assessment not only furthers language development (Gruba & Clark, 2013), but also seems to develop students' self-esteem, independence, and motivation (e.g., Buchanan, 2000; Butler, 1988).

Additionally, instructors are aware of the common occurrence of public speaking anxiety among students and may take steps to accommodate and evaluate them more holistically. They may provide additional support through pre-presentation practice sessions, offer techniques to manage anxiety, or emphasize the importance of effort and content generation rather than focusing solely on the performance aspect. As a result, the instructors' consideration for students' anxiety can mitigate any potential negative impact on grades. The employment of other fun-filled learning assessment to help the students get a good grade could be employed. Cheong et al. (2013) performed research to see if gamification improves learning, enjoyment, and engagement.

Furthermore, it is important to note that some students may excel in written assignments and other coursework while struggling with public speaking. Therefore, grades in subjects that heavily emphasize written work may not be affected by public speaking anxiety. This could explain why there might be no significant correlation observed between personal reports of public speaking anxiety and overall grades. In parallel with the Vygotskian approach, Littlewood (1984) noted that "the development of communicative skills can only take place if learners have the motivation and opportunity to express their own identity and relate with the people around them." It is noted that many instructors allow the use of the native tongue in order to expound topics of

discussion instead of purely resorting to English language in the students' explanation. This is where the comfort zone among students paving the way for a better evaluation.

Ultimately, while public speaking anxiety is a real concern for many individuals, it may not have a direct impact on students' grades. Instructors' grading practices, accommodations, and inclusion of multiple evaluation criteria play a significant role in assessing the overall performance of students, thereby reducing the potential negative effects of public speaking anxiety on grades. The use of technology and social media in the classroom is also a factor in raising students' academic evaluation instead of just the public speaking and oral presentation skills. Some studies (Huah and Jarret, 2014; Parveen, 2016; Stockwell, 2007) revealed that modern technologies such as the Internet, podcasts, websites, applications, videos, online translation and dictionary tools, and social media, etc. had significant effects on improving speaking skills.

In the case of public speaking and oral presentations, instructors are often aware that many students experience anxiety and nervousness. As a result, they might implement alternative evaluation methods or consider multiple criteria when grading these assignments. They understand that anxiety should not be the sole determinant of a student's grade and that it may not accurately reflect their true abilities or knowledge in the subject matter. Instructors can review specific characteristics against pre-established standards and guidelines, theoretically allowing for better student evaluation (Chism, 2007).

For example, instructors may assign grades based on factors such as content knowledge, organization, delivery style, use of visual aids, and overall effort. This allows them to assess the student's performance holistically, considering various aspects of the presentation rather than solely focusing on the anxiety-related aspects.

Additionally, instructors may provide additional support or accommodations for students who experience anxiety. This might include offering practice sessions, sharing techniques to manage anxiety, or creating a supportive environment to help students feel more at ease.

These accommodations can further level the playing field and reduce the negative impact of anxiety on grades. Again, in the pursuit of good practice, technology such as video chatting to remedy personal speaking anxiety can be used by the instructors as an intervention to lessen the worries among students. Al-Abdali (2016) and Sevy-Biloon and Chroman (2019) suggested that the use of video chats had positive effects on the students with minimum opportunities to practice English outside. They found that video chatting let students have more positive feelings and inherent satisfaction about their speaking performances as they provided communication channels in a more relaxing environment.

Ordinal Logistic Regression is a statistical method used to model the relationship between a set of independent variables and an ordinal dependent variable (Singh, 2022).

It is an extension of binary logistic regression where the dependent variable has more than two categories or levels.

In ordinal logistic regression, the dependent variable is not continuous, but it has an inherent ordering or ranking. Examples of ordinal variables include ratings or Likert scale responses that are measured on an ordered scale (e.g., strongly disagree, disagree, neutral, agree, strongly agree). The goal of ordinal logistic regression is to estimate the probability that an observation falls into a particular category or a higher category based on the values of the independent variables. It allows us to examine the impact of the independent variables on the odds of a higher category versus a lower one.

Table 2 reveals that the tribe of students significantly affects their PRPSA level ($Z=-1.99$, $P=0.046$). However, regardless of age, gender, household members and Economic status of students, their PRPSA level remains unaffected ($Z=1.01$, -0.40 , -0.36 , -0.20 , $P=0.313$, 0.687 , 0.715 , 0.845).

The impact of tribe or race on public speaking and oral presentation anxiety can be significant due to various cultural and social factors. It is important to note that generalizations should be avoided, as the experiences and responses to anxiety can vary greatly within and across tribes or races. However, certain cultural and societal factors can influence public speaking anxiety in different ways. Cultural Expectations and Communication Styles: Different tribes or races may have unique cultural expectations and norms regarding public speaking and communication styles.

According to Bingham and Okagaki (2012) "The underachievement of African American, Latino, and American Indian students in the U.S. is linked to poor school engagement. This categorizes influential factors into three domains: student, family, and school. It explores aspects like ethnic identity, discrimination experiences, and bicultural efficacy." This acknowledges the fact that some cultures may place a greater emphasis on verbal expression and confident delivery, while others may prioritize more reserved and modest communication. These cultural expectations can create pressure and anxiety for individuals who may feel they need to meet or conform to these expectations.

Race-related Stereotypes and Discrimination: Myles (2021) revealed that underrepresented racial minority college students attending predominantly privileged race can impede confidence among the minority group students. Members of certain races may face racial stereotypes and discrimination that can affect their confidence and increase anxiety during public speaking. Stereotypes related to communication skills, intelligence, or public presence may create additional pressure or self-doubt, leading to heightened anxiety. These external factors can exacerbate public speaking anxieties and make it more challenging for individuals to overcome their fears.

Language Barriers: Lester et al. (2017) explained that microaggressions may not fall in line with what we would traditionally or legally consider discrimination but takes a big toll in student's performance. For individuals who speak English as a second language or have different dialects, public speaking anxiety can be influenced by language barriers. It is notable that Indiana Aerospace University students come from multifarious races and

that their cultural background affects their public speaking and presentation performances in the classroom. Tribes or races that have distinct dialects or accents may encounter difficulties in expressing themselves in a language that is not their native tongue. Fear of miscommunication, being misunderstood, or facing linguistic discrimination can contribute to increased anxiety during public speaking.

Cultural Values and Conformity: Byars-Winston (2010) argued, educators should assist in providing their students and students' families with tools to explore what meaning can be made from their previous racialized experiences and notions. Cultural values and norms regarding individualism, collectivism, and conformity can also play a role in public speaking anxiety. In some cultures, the emphasis on group harmony and conformity to social norms may create anxiety for individuals who fear standing out or deviating from established patterns. The pressure to conform to cultural expectations can add an extra layer of anxiety when speaking publicly.

On the other hand, the research results show that age and gender do not have a direct causal relationship with public speaking anxiety. Public speaking anxiety can be experienced by individuals of all ages and genders, as it is primarily influenced by personal factors, individual experiences, and psychological mechanisms rather than demographic characteristics.

While it is true that certain age groups or gender stereotypes may have specific societal expectations or norms related to public speaking, it does not mean that every individual within those demographics will experience anxiety to the same degree. Public speaking anxiety is a complex phenomenon that is influenced by a range of factors, including self-perception, past experiences, individual personality traits, and learned behaviors.

Self-perception and Confidence: Public speaking anxiety is often related to self-perception and confidence levels. Individuals who have low self-esteem or lack confidence in their public speaking abilities may experience anxiety irrespective of their age or gender. Papadopoulous (2022) suggests that students in the shared group expressed a significantly more positive opinion in the end-of-activity questionnaire in terms of perceived learning gains and the helpfulness of writing justifications for their answers solely because of self-motivation instead of extrinsic or group encouragements.

Past Experiences, personality traits and learned behaviors do not also affect public speaking and oral presentation anxiety. According to Griffith *et. al.* (2021), the impact of quality on student performance was examined by comparing student performance when taught by excellent faculty and average faculty (determined through administrative evaluations). This means that the grade or evaluation may be high when the teacher provides quality education instead of determining or relying on the student's personal qualities. Previous experiences with public speaking, such as positive or negative feedback, supportive or judgmental environments, and past successes or failures, play a significant role in the development of public speaking anxiety. These experiences can be unique to individuals and are not solely dependent on age or gender. In the specific field

of psychophysiological there has been an increasing interest in studying gender stress reactivity (Carrillo et al., 2001; Davis & Matthews, 1996; Girdler et al., 1997; Lash et al., 1995; Matthews et al., 1991; Steptoe et al., 1996). Carrillo et al. (2001) concluded that gender could act as a moderator but not as a cause for different performances.

Personality traits, such as introversion or extroversion, can influence public speaking anxiety. However, these traits are not tied directly to age or gender and can vary greatly within each demographic group. If individuals have observed others experiencing anxiety during public speaking or have learned to associate public speaking with negative consequences, they may develop anxiety regardless of their age or gender.

It is essential to recognize that public speaking anxiety is a common phenomenon that can affect anyone. While certain age groups or genders may face distinct societal expectations related to communication or public speaking, these expectations alone do not determine the level of anxiety an individual may experience. Moreover, it is also worth noting that individuals can develop strategies and techniques to manage and overcome public speaking anxiety regardless of age or gender. With proper support, practice, and exposure, individuals can improve their public speaking skills and reduce anxiety associated with public speaking, regardless of demographic factors.

Results also show that household members and economic status also do not have a direct influence on public speaking and oral presentations. While there might be certain indirect factors related to economic status that can affect public speaking anxiety, it is important to understand that it is not a determining factor on its own. Here are some reasons why household members and economic status do not significantly affect public speaking and oral presentations:

Public speaking anxiety is primarily driven by personal factors and individual experiences. It is influenced by factors such as self-confidence, past experiences, learned behaviors, and individual personality traits. These factors are not solely dependent on household members or economic status, but rather on an individual's internal characteristics and experiences. With a supportive environment, the presence or absence of supportive household members can indeed have an impact on an individual's confidence and self-esteem. However, it is not a consistent or determinative factor for public speaking anxiety. According to Muyan (2017) Some individuals may have supportive household members who encourage and boost their confidence, while others may not have that kind of support but can still develop their public speaking skills and manage anxiety through other means, such as training, practice, or participation in supportive communities.

Access to Resources: Economic status can indirectly influence public speaking anxiety through access to resources. For example, individuals from lower-income households might have limited access to public speaking training, classes, or resources. However, it is important to note that access to resources or training alone does not guarantee the absence or presence of public speaking anxiety. Problems of online education were not only limited to internet and technological access but the relevance of

curriculum for this mode of education was also a major concern of the university students (Adnan, 2020). Many individuals with limited resources have developed effective public speaking skills and overcome anxiety through perseverance, self-study, or alternative means of acquiring knowledge and practice, such as online resources or peer support.

Individual Effort and Motivation: Regardless of household members or economic status, an individual's effort, determination, and motivation play a crucial role in their ability to improve their public speaking skills and manage anxiety. With self-motivation, disciplined practice, and a growth mindset, individuals can develop their public speaking abilities regardless of their household members or economic status.

Ultimately, while household members and economic status may indirectly influence public speaking anxiety, they do not serve as determining factors. Personal factors, individual experiences, access to resources, and individual effort and motivation are more significant factors in overcoming public speaking anxiety and developing effective oral presentation skills.

Theme Cluster 1: Feeling during Class Presentation

The ability to effectively deliver a speech is often regarded as essential for graduates' success in the workplace (Smith & Sodano, 2011; van Ginkel et al., 2019), as well as for achieving career advancement and participating meaningfully in democratic society (Chan, 2011). However, students' experiences during classroom oral presentations can vary significantly, though certain common themes emerge.

Nervousness is a prevalent feeling, with many students experiencing anxiety before and during presentations. This response is typical, as speaking in front of an audience often involves being the center of attention. Another frequent emotion is the fear of judgment, where students worry about how they will be perceived by peers or the instructor. Concerns about making mistakes or receiving negative feedback can heighten this fear.

A lack of confidence is also common, as some students doubt their public speaking abilities. They may fear forgetting important information or stumbling over their words. The pressure to perform well adds to the stress, as students strive to meet academic expectations and impress both classmates and instructors.

In addition, students may feel self-conscious about their appearance, voice, or body language, fearing they might look or sound awkward. Finally, overwhelming stage fright can occur in more severe cases, leading to intense anxiety and physical symptoms such as sweating, trembling, or a racing heart.

Theme Cluster 2: The Reasons or Causes of the Participants' Presentation Anxiety

Public Speaking Anxiety (PSA), a specific form of social anxiety disorder, is characterized by an intense fear of social performance, often due to concerns about being negatively judged. This fear can cause individuals to feel anxious about acting in a way that might be perceived as embarrassing or incompetent. During classroom presentations, students frequently experience recurring anxieties, with common themes including fear of judgment, lack of experience, self-consciousness, and performance pressure. These factors heighten anxiety as students worry about making mistakes, being scrutinized by peers, or failing to meet expectations.

Additional causes of PSA include the fear of forgetting important information or freezing during a presentation, as well as perfectionistic tendencies, where students strive for flawless delivery. Lack of confidence further exacerbates their anxiety, as students doubt their abilities to engage the audience or present effectively. All these factors contribute to the stress and discomfort many students feel when faced with public speaking situations, highlighting the multifaceted nature of PSA.

Theme Cluster 3: The Factors that Contribute Most to the Presentation Anxiety

Pertaub et al. (2001) conducted studies on audience reactions, exploring how a speaker's anxiety is influenced by different types of feedback from a virtual audience (positive, negative, or neutral). Their findings align with common themes revealed by participants regarding the factors contributing to presentation anxiety. One major factor is the fear of judgment and criticism, where the concern over making mistakes or receiving negative feedback heightens anxiety. Additionally, lack of experience and negative past experiences in public speaking contribute significantly, as individuals unfamiliar with presentations or those who have faced public embarrassment tend to feel more anxious. Self-consciousness about one's appearance, voice, or body language further increases anxiety, as individuals worry about how others perceive them.

Other factors include perfectionism and high expectations, where individuals strive for flawless delivery, creating immense pressure. A lack of preparation exacerbates anxiety, leading to fear of forgetting key points or being unable to handle questions. Lastly, glossophobia—the inherent fear of public speaking itself—plays a major role in amplifying anxiety. These factors often overlap, and addressing presentation anxiety requires recognizing these influences and adopting strategies such as thorough preparation, seeking feedback, practicing relaxation techniques, and reframing negative thoughts to build confidence and reduce stress.

Theme Cluster 4: Ways to Deal with their Presentation Anxiety

In recent years, literature has accumulated valuable insights into effective classroom practices for teaching oral presentation skills (OPS). González-Zamar and Abad Segura (2020) highlight the increasing focus on practical classroom experiences,

while Boetje and van Ginkel (2020) emphasize the critical role of practice in developing oral skills. Managing presentation anxiety, an obstacle for many students, requires a combination of preparation, practice, and targeted strategies. Participants in various studies consistently emphasized the importance of thorough preparation, organizing content, and practicing multiple times to increase confidence and reduce anxiety.

Key strategies for reducing presentation anxiety include familiarizing oneself with the presentation environment, visualizing success, and practicing relaxation techniques like deep breathing. Positive self-talk and reframing negative thoughts into affirmations also help boost confidence. Engaging with the audience through eye contact and confident body language, starting with a strong opening, and seeking feedback from supportive peers or mentors further enhance one's ability to manage anxiety and deliver an effective presentation. These practical steps combine to create a solid foundation for building both oral skills and presentation confidence.

Conclusions

This research study concludes that public speaking and oral presentation anxiety among students does not have a significant effect on their Grade Point Average. In terms of the students' profile, the tribe of students significantly affects their PRPSA level. However, regardless of age, gender, household members and Economic status of students, their PRPSA level remains unaffected.

The most common themes and properties revealed that the students feel nervous, afraid of judgments, lack of confidence, pressure, self-consciousness and overwhelming stage fright during oral presentations. These are reaffirmed in their reasons or causes of presentation anxiety adding the concept of perfectionism that intensify their fears. The most common themes that contribute to their anxiety include fear of judgment, lack of experience, negative past experience, self-consciousness, high expectations, lack of preparation and the fear of public speaking itself. The most common themes of dealing with anxiety reveal good preparation, familiarization of environment, practice, positivity, meditation and relaxation, reframing, engaging with audience, starting a good opening, seeking support and gaining valuable experience.

In conclusion, public speaking and oral presentation anxiety could vary in effects to students in their academic life. One can deter the effects of public speaking anxiety by gaining more experience and building self-confidence.

Recommendations

The research provides several recommendations aimed at mitigating the effects of public speaking anxiety among students through policy-making and school-based training. Key suggestions include raising awareness about public speaking anxiety among students, educators, and administrators by developing education programs that focus on its prevalence and impact, as well as strategies to manage it. Establishing supportive

learning environments with smaller class sizes, student support services, and anxiety accommodations is also vital. Additionally, incorporating public speaking training into the curriculum from a young age can help students gradually develop their communication skills, while professional development for educators is recommended to help them create inclusive environments.

Further recommendations involve promoting alternative assessment methods, such as written assignments or multimedia presentations, to accommodate students with severe public speaking anxiety. Mental health support within schools, including access to counselors and reducing stigma, is crucial for addressing anxiety. Lastly, funding and collaboration for research on public speaking anxiety should be encouraged to inform evidence-based policies and interventions. Implementing these strategies will foster inclusive education, enhance students' learning experiences, and support their development of effective communication skills.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This paper follows the ethical consideration perspective of Creswell (2014). The authors affirmed their commitment to ethical research practices, including obtaining informed consent from all participants and ensuring their freedom to withdraw from the study at any time without penalty. The anonymity of the participants was maintained throughout the research process, safeguarding their well-being. The authors also confirmed that no conflict of interest existed in the conduct of the study, that plagiarism had been strictly avoided, and that the interpretation of findings was free from bias. Furthermore, the results of this study were intended solely for research purposes.

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